

Development of an Excel-Based Room Reservation System to Address Peak Holiday Periods

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Abstract: In the current era, the majority of Thai employees, whether in the private or government sector, share common holiday periods for relaxation and travel, such as Songkran or the New Year. During holiday seasons, a significant number of people often plan trips to different provinces simultaneously, resulting in a chaotic situation when it comes to booking accommodations due to high demand. The problem that arises is that guests are unable to determine the availability of rooms, suitable rooms based on their preferences and budget, and make informed decisions. Therefore, this project group took a keen interest in addressing these issues and collaborated to design a room reservation system using Excel software to alleviate these challenges. The objectives of this project are as follows, 1) To apply knowledge gained from coursework to everyday life. 2) To enhance convenience for both employees and guests. 3) To facilitate decision-making for guests in their accommodation planning. In the course of this project, the team conducted a comprehensive study of various Excel program features and principles to design a room reservation system that can display the following functionalities: 1) A "Book Registration" page for room reservation. 2) A calendar displaying available booking dates. 3) Display of reservation history and the option to cancel bookings. 4) Presentation of an annual summary of room reservations. The results of this project reveal that the Excel-based room reservation system effectively reduces complexity for both employees and guests, providing enhanced convenience and efficiency for system users.

Keywords: *Excel, VBA, Book Registration, Reservation System.*

1. Introduction

Thailand is a very popular tourist destination among tourists around the world. In 2018, Thailand had as many as 39.9 million tourists. The tourism industry was able to generate more than 300 billion baht in income for the country. At the same time, problems the density of tourists is also something that must be urgently resolved. Because the Thai tourism industry has continued to grow at 2.83 percent, the travel behavior of most Thai people will be traveling for tourism 1-3 times per year, accounting for 31.61 percent, and more than 83.78 percent is traveling. During the holidays and groups of

tourists traveled on their own (92.37 percent) [1] Later in 2029, a new strain of coronavirus (COVID-19) occurred, resulting in the tourism industry being greatly affected. In 2019, the number of tourists decreased to only 6.70 million, or a decrease equivalent to 83.21 percent [2]. Experts have analyzed the trend of tourism in Thailand since 2021, there will be a better trend. and return to normal in 2024, as shown in Figs. 1.

Figs. 1. The Number of Tourists each year

But from the improved economic situation and tourism trends that are starting to return to normal. But at the same time, the problem of crowding during the holiday still remains. Therefore, we should be prepared to deal with problems that may arise. Both in terms of traveling to various tourist attractions and accommodation locations that are not conducive to allowing guests to conveniently and appropriately check available rooms and prices. From the complete report of the Office of the Permanent Secretary, Ministry of Tourism and Sports. Cost project for surveying attitudes and satisfaction of Thai and foreign tourists traveling in Thailand (2020) has surveyed the satisfaction of tourists in Thailand in terms of accommodations. The survey found that tourists are less satisfied, from 83.2% satisfaction in 2019, reduced to 80.6% in 2020, the main reason being the difficulty in contacting and booking rooms with hotels. The number of rooms is not enough to meet the needs of tourists. Including the inappropriateness of the price and quality of the rooms. The researcher is therefore interested in developing a room reservation system by applying Microsoft Excel with Visual Basic for Application (VBA) to write a program to design a room reservation system to solve the problems that

arise from reservations. rooms during travel because Microsoft Excel VBA is an automatic program that can help with analysis Creating forms, forecasts, creating graphics, and more using VBA programming has the advantage of reducing errors in your work. Save time and work automatically [3,4]. This research aims to develop a room reservation system by applying Excel VBA in system design. and test the use of the system by a sample group to take the room booking system program that has been designed and develop it further in the future.

2. Research Methodology

This research is to design a room reservation system by applying the Excel VBA program to solve the difficulties that may arise from the density of tourists. Therefore, in conducting research the study steps can be shown as shown in Figs. 2.

Figs. 2. The Flow Chart of Research methodology

This research has a process of conducting research. as follows

1. Literature Review: Study related research to find guidelines for conducting research.
2. Observation: Observe tourists who reserve rooms via telephone or intermediary websites in order to bring out weak points to develop the room reservation system in this research.
3. Designing program: Design an appropriate room reservation system program.
4. Check the program: Check the usage of the program with the developer. If it can be used without defects, it will enter the verification process by users.
5. Testing: Test the program with real users.
6. Evaluate: Evaluate satisfaction and various suggestions for further development in the future.

3. Results

3.1 Program Implementation

In the process of creating a room booking program with VBA Excel, it is necessary to create a program view (Program view) in writing the system by making Data Flow Diagrams (DFD). This step is Process models known as data flow diagrams., are used to explain how data moves through a system and the activities or data processing that the system undertakes [5]. The Data Flow Diagram (DFD) uniform ordering information system on each level is described using the De Marco and Jourdan notation. by in this research, a Data Flow Diagram was created as shown in Figs. 3.

Figs. 3. Data Flow Diagram (DFD) of Booking Reservation Process

From the Data Flow Diagram of the room booking program, it starts with the Customer entering the room booking system. After that, the customer will fill in various information, including Check in, check out, Room number, Customer name, Telephone No. After that, the system will display information back, including Price/Day, Room Available. When the customer checks various information Complete and press the New Book button. The system will record the reservation in the system. and display the confirmed booking results on the Calendar, Calculate and Summary (Report Pivot) pages for the operator or those involved in data management.

3.2 Program Display

The booking program page contains a registration page for customers to make reservations. Calendar page showing available dates for your stay. Database page. System reservation page for operators. The details are as follows:

• Booking Reservation Display

The Booking Reservation page is the home page of the room reservation system. As shown in Figs. 4., the customer will fill in personal information, including first name, last name, and telephone number. Then choose the day to check in and check out, including choosing the room type if the room type and days of stay are available. The system will automatically calculate the days of stay and the amount. But in case the room is not available, the system will show red to notify the guest that on the day and the selected room is Unavailable.

Figs. 4. Booking Reservation display

But in the case that the room is not available on the day the customer chooses the system will notify you by showing almost red. To notify guests that on the selected date and room Unavailable, as shown in Figs. 5., the customer must choose to reserve a new date or change the type of room they are staying in.

Figs. 5. Unavailable Booking Reservation display

• Calendar Display

On this calendar page is a page showing the days when each room type is available. In the case where the room is on different days, the system will show up in red and show the guest's name and telephone number. As shown in Figs. 6., this calendar page is intended to allow operators or administrators to know which room types are being reserved on which day and have access to guest information.

Figs. 6. Calendar display

• Database Display

On the Database Display, it is a page for accommodation administrators to change the type of information in terms of room type, day, month, year, and room reservation status. As shown in Figs. 7., this page is a page to facilitate administrators to modify and add information more easily.

Room Type	Year	Month	Day	Status
VIP01 King Bed 5,000	2023	Jan	1	Booking
VIP02 King Bed 5,000	2024	Feb	2	Cancel
A4 Twin Bed 4,000	2024	Mar	3	
A5 Twin Bed 4,000		Apr	4	
A6 Twin Bed 4,000		May	5	
A7 Twin Bed 4,000		Jun	6	
A8 Twin Bed 4,000		Jul	7	
A9 Twin Bed 4,000		Aug	8	
B1 Twin Bed 3,500		Sep	9	
B2 Twin Bed 3,500		Oct	10	
B3 Twin Bed 3,500		Nov	11	
B4 Twin Bed 3,500		Dec	12	
B5 Double Bed 3,000			13	
B6 Double Bed 3,000			14	
B7 Double Bed 3,000			15	
B8 Double Bed 3,000			16	
C1 Twin Bed 2,000			17	
C2 Twin Bed 2,000			18	
C3 Twin Bed 2,000			19	
C4 Twin Bed 2,000			20	
C5 Double Bed 1,000			21	
C6 Double Bed 1,000			22	
C7 Double Bed 1,000			23	
C8 Double Bed 1,000			24	
			25	
			26	
			27	
			28	
			29	
			30	
			31	

Figs. 7. Database Display

• Summary Data Display

When the customer has completed filling out their stay information and Confirmed Reservation. The system will collect booking information and display it on the Summary data display page, as shown in Figs. 8. This Display page will collect the amount of each booking by different types of rooms and sum the amount for each. This year allows operators to know the income and popular room types so that the information can be used to further develop rooms in the future.

Room No.	VIP01	C8	C1	B1	A4	Grand Total
จำนวนการจอง (ห้อง)	1	0	0	1	0	3
จำนวนที่เข้าพัก	3	0	0	2	5	10
รายได้รวม	15000	0	0	4000	17500	165000
จำนวนการจอง (ห้อง)	2	0	1	0	0	4
จำนวนที่เข้าพัก	8	0	5	0	0	2
รายได้รวม	80000	0	5000	0	0	80000
จำนวนการจอง (ห้อง)	0	1	0	0	0	1
จำนวนที่เข้าพัก	0	12	0	0	0	2
รายได้รวม	0	10000	0	0	0	10000
รวมจำนวนการจอง (ห้อง)	3	1	1	1	1	8
รวมจำนวนที่เข้าพัก	11	2	5	2	5	27
รวมรายได้รวม	165000	10000	5000	4000	17500	80000
						823500

Figs. 8. The Flow Chart of Research methodology

4. Discussion

This research is a design of a room reservation system by applying the Excel VBA program with the aim of solving the problem of difficulties that may arise from the density of tourists. After creating a room reservation system, it was found that the reservation system can reserve rooms and display the results to both customers and operators. But there are still some parts that need to be further developed for greater convenience and beauty of the system.

5. Conclusions

This research focuses on designing a room reservation system to solve the difficulties that may arise from the overcrowding of tourists making room reservations. By applying the Excel VBA program to help reduce the hassle of booking rooms. This program can work in an automatic way, helping with analysis, creating forms, and creating graphs to increase efficiency and reduce errors. Responds to travelers' needs and helps simplify the entire booking process. This helps benefit the business and user experience.

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